

Financial Literacy and Individual Over-Indebtedness in Rwanda: A Case of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro, Nyamasheke District 2015-2019

Author's Details:

^aMuhawenayo Trojan ^bAlbert O. Maake, PhD

^a Graduate Program Student / University of Lay Adventist of Kigali, Kigali campus

^b Lecturer/Faculty of Economic Sciences and Management / University of Lay Adventists of Kigali, Kigali Campus

ABSTRACT

Background: *The low participation of households in financial system is common in rural areas of Rwanda and other developing countries. Fear and limited access to financial institutions constitute major factors explaining this and it threatens household financial wellbeing. To address these threats the government of Rwanda adopted a new national financial policy in 2008 setting up Umurenge SACCOs however against their expected impact on improving household financial wellbeing, most borrowers in these financial institutions are over-indebted which increases their exposure to credit default risk. In 2019 umurenge SACCOs had the highest debt of Frw 5,587,021,359 in non-performing loans equivalent to 11.76% that is beyond the required threshold of 5% and some of these non-performing loans started being written-off. This is detrimental to economic development and causes social problems at a personal level as well as the economy at large. Therefore, the aim of this paper was to assess whether individuals with the higher level of financial literacy have better financial management skills, which reduces the risk of falling into over-indebtedness.*

Method: *The study adopted both qualitative and quantitative approaches to collect data from a sample of 357 respondents selected from the target population of 3279 clients using Solvin's formula. 3 staff and 3 presidents of the board, audit and credit committees of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro were selected purposively. Data were collected using questionnaire and interview guide and analyzed using SPSS Pearson's Correlation Test and Multinomial logistic regression model.*

Results: *To assess the level of financial literacy among U-SACCO clients under the period of study the researchers used the descriptive statistics. The results showed that on the total of 357 clients, 9 (2.5%), do not have knowledge related to financial literacy at all, 98 (27.5%) had financial knowledge, 81 (22.7%) had the financial skill, 58 (16.2%) had financial attitude, 75 (21.0%) had financial behaviour and 36 (10.1%) had financial awareness. To find out the extent to which financial literacy affects individual over-indebtedness among U-SACCO clients the researchers used Pearson Chi-Square test in SPSS. The results showed that the found value of this metric appeared to be 121.971, that is Pearson Chi-Square = 121.971 with a corresponding p-value = .001. With a cut-off (level of significance = 5%), the researchers noticed this p-value <.05, and thus there was an association of the financial literacy and individual over-indebtedness of the clients in the area under study. To establish the relationship between financial literacy and individual over-indebtedness among U-SACCO clients for the period under study. The researchers used Multinomial Logistic Regression Model. The results showed that in the training set of six explanatory variables, there were only three variables namely: education, financial literacy, and the time spent working with U-SACCO clients that contributed significantly to the outcome variable while others like monthly income, marital status, and gender were dropped from the model since they could not affect the individual over-indebtedness of clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro in the area under study.*

Conclusion: *The factor that could be taken first into consideration to overcome the individual over-indebtedness must be "education" towards the financial skills required in the loan-related businesses. Most people working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro in the year under study had primary education, most of the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro have financial literacy under the category of financial knowledge. There was a significant association between financial literacy and the individual over-indebtedness status of the*

clients under study. "Education" was the first variable that came before financial literacy in explaining the outcome variable, and the main factors that influence all the individual over-indebtedness status of the clients were found to be education, financial literacy and the time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro.

Key words: *Financial Literacy, and Over-Indebtedness*

INTRODUCTION

The low financial participation among households is common in rural areas of Rwanda and other developing countries. Fear and limited access to financial institutions constitute major factors explaining this low financial participation and threatening household financial wellbeing. To address these threats to household financial wellbeing, the government of Rwanda adopted a new national financial policy in 2008 setting up Umurenge SACCOs. Since then, the major objectives of Umurenge SACCOs have been to increase households' access to financial institutions across all districts of the country. In particular, financial policies that promote the decentralization of financial institutions and encourage households to participate in financial institutions can improve rural households' attitudes toward accepting financial institutions and have positive outcomes on their financial attitudes and wellbeing.

Against their expected impact on improving household financial wellbeing, most borrowers in these financial institutions are over-indebted which increases their exposure to credit default risk. The rate of non-performing loans across Umurenge SACCOs is considerably higher than the national tolerable rate of 5% recommended by the National Bank of Rwanda. In 2019, about 12% of the total loans issued by Umurenge SACCOs or Frw: 5.6 billion were classified under non-performing loans, Rwanda Cooperative Agency (2019), BNR (2018).

Holding excessive debts caused severe consequences for the national financial system and has degenerated household financial wellbeing. The most cited financial consequences include: increased household financial distress (e.g., freezing of the properties of the defaulters; holding salaries of government officials who are defaulters; defaulters being taken to courts, and ruin of the reputation of Umurenge SACCOs) and liquidity crisis across Umurenge SACCOs (RCA, 2019; BNR, 2018).

There is inadequate information regarding borrowers' financial characteristics behind holding excessive credits from Umurenge SACCOs and why most of credits issued by these financial institutions end in non-performing loans. As a first step toward a systematic understanding of these problems, the researchers conducted a survey of 357 clients of Umurenge SACCOs to understand how their financial literacy levels relate to their financial attitudes towards financial services provided by Umurenge SACCOs.

In particular, it is documented that financial literacy determines the probability of borrowing and size of loan obtained, (Disney & Gathergood, 2013; Lusardi & Mitchell (2014). Failure to justify debt is associated with lower financial literacy, Lusardi & Tufano (2015). Lower financial literacy explains frequent financial mistakes, Agarwal et al. (2009); Stango & Zinman (2009) such as the use of high cost methods of borrowing, Moore (2003); Lusardi and Scheresberg (2013) and inability to decipher financial concepts and terms of credit, Disney & Gathergood (2013). Consequently, low financial literacy levels could explain excessive credits among the clients of Umurenge SACCOs and the high rate of non-performing loans issued by these financial institutions.

Yet our understanding of how borrowers' financial literacy explains the performance of loans issued by Umurenge SACCOs is limited. Therefore, this study tries to answer the following question: Are Umurenge SACCOs' less financially literate clients more likely to hold excessive loans compared to highly financially literate clients?, How do the management of received credit and the level of credit default risk differ according to the Umurenge SACCOs' borrowers' financial literacy levels? For the purpose of this research, these questions were answered.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The Life Cycle/Permanent Income Theory by Modigliani Brumberg in 1954 and Friedman, 1957

Individuals consume by borrowing in the periods of low-income and saving during high income. People spend money in relation to expected long-term average income. It predicts the drivers of over-indebtedness and unpredicted adverse shocks to the consumer's expenditure requirements.

Behavioural-Life-Cycle Theory by Shefrin and Thaler, 1988

Individuals are tempted to spend all their resources on current consumption instead of saving, Individuals who save, overcome self-control problem by investing and a person's consumption spending not only depends on total wealth but also on how it is allocated among assets. Behavioral approach is one of the fundamental means of explaining over-indebtedness.

Self-efficacy and Goal setting theory of motivation by Albert Bandura 1986 and Edwin Locke in 1960

Social cognitive theories that deal with the personal judgment of how an individual can execute courses of action required to deal with prospective situations. It can predicts the level of individual financial literacy through the use of less credit cards, control debt, and financial planning.

METHOD

Study population, Study area and Study design

The study population consisted of the clients, employees and the presidents of the board, audit and credit committees of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro. Simple random and purposive sampling were used to select 357 clients, 3 employees and 3 presidents of the Board, audit and credit committees of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro. Questionnaire and interview guide were used to collect Primary data and Secondary data among the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro.

Inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria

The study included clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro of Nyamasheke district, Rangiro sector who took the loan at least once from 2015-2019. They were selected randomly prior to the calculated sample population in the sector. In contrast, the study excluded respondents without consent agreement of participation in the study and the ones who did not take the loan in the period under study.

Ethical approval and consent

After presenting and reviewing the research proposal for its relevance, the letter of permission was obtained from University of Lay Adventist of Kigali and was presented to the President of the board and the manager of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro for permission to conduct the study. The participation in the interview was an absolute voluntary decision, the verbal consents were obtained from all the respondents before data collection start. Each collected data were treated with utmost sincerity and the results were used for research purposes only.

Statistical analysis

Data were cleaned, coded and entered into SPSS version 20. Analysis was done at univariate, bivariate and multivariate levels. At univariate level, frequencies were computed whereas the bivariate and multivariate analyses such Pearson Chi-Square test in SPSS and Multinomial Logistic Regression model were used to analyze the association between financial literacy and individual over-indebtedness. The level of statistical significance was set at P value < 0.05 . Multinomial Logistic Regression model was performed to establish the relationship between financial literacy and individual over-indebtedness among U-SACCO clients for the period under study.

For this study, the logistic regression extend to models with multiple explanatory variables. Let k denotes the number of predictors for a binary response y by x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k . The model for log odds is:

$$\text{Logit}[p(Y = 1)] = \alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \dots + \beta_kx_k.$$

And the alternative formula, directly specifying $\pi(x)$, is:

$$\pi(x) = \frac{\exp(\alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \dots + \beta_kx_k)}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \dots + \beta_kx_k)}$$

The parameter β_i refers to the effect of x_i on the log odds that $y = 1$, controlling other x_j , for instance, $\exp(\beta_i)$ is the multiplicative effect on the odds of one-unit increase in x_i , at fixed levels of x_j . Increase in x_i , at fixed levels of x_j .

Since all the π 's add to unity, this reduces to:

$$\log[\pi_j(x_i)] = \frac{\exp(\alpha_{0i} + \beta_{1j}x_{1i} + \beta_{2j}x_{2i} + \dots + \beta_{pj}x_{pi})}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \exp(\alpha_{0i} + \beta_{1j}x_{1i} + \beta_{2j}x_{2i} + \dots + \beta_{pj}x_{pi})}$$

For $j = 1, 2, \dots, (k - 1)$, the model parameters are estimated by the method of maximum likelihood estimation.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic characteristics of the Clients at SACCO Wisigara Rangiro

A total of 6 staff working at SACCO Wisigara Rangiro that participated in this study was composed of 4 (66.7%) males and 2 (33.3%) females. They were 2 females the two were in age between 20-30 years old and their working experience ranged between two and five years. And the remaining portion of this working staff was aged between 30-40 years old with more than five years of experience.

The majorities of the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro were married 197 (55.2%) while single clients were 160 (44.8%). Those who completed primary education were 197 (55.2%), secondary education certificate 156 (43.7%) and university 4 (1.1%). The total number of clients who worked with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro was 357 from whom 161 (45.1%) were females and 196 (54.9%) were males. Age group was variant in all stages, (40.7%), between 20-30 years 82 (23 %), between 31-40 years 170 (47.6%) and above 40 years 105 (29.4%).

Table 1 1: Marital Status

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Married	197	55.2	55.2	55.2
	Single	160	44.8	44.8	100.0
	Total	357	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Education

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Primary	197	55.2	55.2	55.2
	Secondary	156	43.7	43.7	98.9
	University	4	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	357	100.0	100.0	

Table 3: Gender

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	161	45.1	45.1	45.1
	Male	196	54.9	54.9	100.0
	Total	357	100.0	100.0	

Table 4: Age-group

	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 20-30	82	23.0	23.0	23.0
31-41	170	47.6	47.6	70.6
>41	105	29.4	29.4	100.0
Total	357	100.0	100.0	

Level of financial literacy among the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro.

To assess the level of financial literacy among the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro under the period of study, the researchers recorded the frequencies related to the questions responded by the clients and these records yielded a tangible proof of this level using the output extract from SPSS.

0 stands for the base category of financial literacy and this means that the number of clients who do not know anything related to financial literacy at all was 9 (2.5%), those who had financial knowledge were 98 (27.5%), 81 (22.7%) had the financial skill, 58 (16.2%) had financial attitude, 75 (21.0%) had financial behaviour and 36 (10.1%) had financial awareness

Status of individual over-indebtedness among the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro clients

To begin with, 4 (1.1%) of the clients were out of over-indebtedness status, 54 (15.1%) were in over-indebtedness status under financial distress, 192 (53.8%) were in over-indebtedness status under regular arrears, 33 (9.2 %) were in over-indebtedness status under foreclosure, 24 (6.7%) were in over-indebtedness status under high debt to income ratio and 50 (14%) were in the over-indebtedness status under the level of making heavy use of credit

Table 7: Financial .Literacy

	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid .0	9	2.5	2.5	2.5
1.0	98	27.5	27.5	30.0
2.0	81	22.7	22.7	52.7
3.0	58	16.2	16.2	68.9
4.0	75	21.0	21.0	89.9
5.0	36	10.1	10.1	100.0
Total	357	100.0	100.0	

Table 5: Individual.Over-indebtedness

	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid .0	4	1.1	1.1	1.1
1.0	54	15.1	15.1	16.2
2.0	192	53.8	53.8	70.0
3.0	33	9.2	9.2	79.3
4.0	24	6.7	6.7	86.0
5.0	50	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	357	100.0	100.0	

Table 6: Financial Literacy * I.O Cross tabulation

Count

		I.O						Total
		.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	
F.L	.0	0	1	1	4	3	0	9
	1.0	4	17	60	2	2	13	98
	2.0	0	15	40	5	6	15	81
	3.0	0	16	21	12	8	1	58
	4.0	0	4	35	10	5	21	75
	5.0	0	1	35	0	0	0	36
Total	4	54	192	33	24	50	357	

Financial literacy over individual over-indebtedness status of the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro

The cross-tabulation yielded the information of financial literacy with all its levels over individual over-indebtedness status with all its levels of all the clients under study.

It was observed that that no clients who did not know anything about financial literacy and at the same time being in individual over-indebtedness, there was only one client who knew something about financial literacy and being in over-indebtedness status under financial distress category. Finally there were 36 clients who had the financial awareness but being in individual over-indebtedness status under the making heavy use of credit category.

Association of financial literacy and individual over-indebtedness

To check whether financial literacy affects the individual over-indebtedness status of the clients in the area under study, the researchers applied the Pearson Chi-Square test for association in SPSS to test for the association of the variables under study. The Pearson Chi-Square findings indicated a 121.971 with a corresponding p-value = .001. With a cutoff (level of significance = 5%), the researchers observed that the p-value was <.05 and thus there is an association of the financial literacy and individual over-indebtedness status of the clients in the area under study.

Table 8: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	121.971 ^a	25	.001
Likelihood Ratio	126.856	25	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.238	1	.266
N of Valid Cases	357		

A training set of explanatory variables that contribute significantly to the outcome variable

To determine the factors that influence the individual over-indebtedness status of the clients working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro, the researchers attempted to use the NOMREG command in SPSS. Below are some outputs of this command.

The case processing summary table shows number of observations that was in each category of the outcome variable as well as their percentages. The model fitting information shows various indices for assessing the intercept only model (sometimes referred to as the null model) and the final model which includes all the explanatory variables. With a p-value (= .000) of the final model which is less than the cutoff (= .05), the researchers noticed that there was a significant difference between the null model and the full model that describes the relationship between the outcome variable and the explanatory variables.

Table 9: Model Fitting Information

Model	Model Fitting Criteria			Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	AIC	BIC	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	958.929	978.318	948.929			
Final	838.300	1051.575	728.300	220.630	50	.000

		N	Marginal Percentage
I.O	.0	4	1.1%
	1.0	54	15.1%
	2.0	192	53.8%
	3.0	33	9.2%
	4.0	24	6.7%
	5.0	50	14.0%
Gender	.0	161	45.1%
	1.0	196	54.9%
Educ	1.0	197	55.2%
	2.0	156	43.7%
	3.0	4	1.1%
M.Status	1.0	197	55.2%
	2.0	160	44.8%
F.L	.0	9	2.5%
	1.0	98	27.5%
	2.0	81	22.7%
	3.0	58	16.2%
	4.0	75	21.0%
	5.0	36	10.1%
Valid		357	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		357	
Subpopulation		342 ^a	

Case Processing Summary of the Model

Next is to determine the goodness-of-fit of the final model that includes all the explanatory variables and to do this, the researchers examined the metrics extracted from SPSS. The interpretation of the available statistical metrics can be understood in the way that the Pearson Chi-Square and Deviance Chi-Square all have a p-value (= 1.000) which is greater than the cutoff (= 0.05), thus the final model overall fits well the data than the null model.

An alternative way to check the goodness-of-fit is the likelihood ratio Chi-square test. The researchers observed that in the training set of all explanatory variables, (the time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro coded as "Time", monthly income coded as "M.income", education coded as "Educ", gender-coded as "Gender", marital status coded as "M.status" and financial literacy coded as "F.L") education, financial literacy, and the time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro are the variables that contributed significantly to the outcome. Such a decision could be made using the fact the p-values corresponding to the Chi-Square metrics of these three explanatory variables are all less than the cutoff (= .05). Thus individual over-indebtedness status of the clients at SACCO Wisigara Rangiro was influenced by three explanatory variables, such as education, time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro and financial literacy. The remaining independent variables like gender, marital status and monthly income could be dropped from the model and the overall fit would not be significantly reduced.

Table 10: Goodness-of-Fit of a Statistical Model

	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	10121195.341	1655	1.000
Deviance	715.823	1655	1.000

Table 10: Likelihood Ratio Tests

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria			Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	AIC of Reduced Model	BIC of Reduced Model	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	838.300	1051.575	728.300 ^a	.000	0	.
Time	842.311	1036.198	742.311 ^b	14.011	5	.016
M.Income	834.840	1028.726	734.840 ^b	6.540	5	.257
Gender	813.250	1007.137	713.250 ^b	.	5	.078
Educ	1022.670	1216.557	922.670 ^b	194.370	5	.000
M.Status	838.300	1051.575	728.300 ^a	.000	0	.098
F.L	836.244	952.576	776.244 ^b	47.944	25	.004

To compute the parameter estimates of the model, a maximum likelihood estimation procedure was used and yielded the logistic coefficient (β) for each predictor variable for each alternative category of the outcome variable (table below).

Table 11: Parameter Estimates

I.O ^a	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1.0	Intercept	7.285	5.026	2.101	1	.147		
	Time	.071	.046	2.390	1	.122	1.074	.981 1.175
	M.Income	.000	.000	.012	1	.913	1.000	1.000 1.000
	[Gender=.0]	1.622	1.010	2.581	1	.108	5.064	.700 36.634
	[Gender=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Educ=1.0]	-8.060	1.114	52.377	1	.000	.000	3.562E-5 .003
	[Educ=2.0]	-9.546	.000	.	1	.	7.149E-5	7.149E-5 7.149E-5
	[Educ=3.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[M.Status=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[M.Status=2.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[F.L=.0]	4.374	18.071	.059	1	.809	79.364	3.293E-14 191290120131114432.000
	[F.L=1.0]	-1.407	4.470	.099	1	.753	.245	3.834E-5 1562.970
	[F.L=2.0]	1.817	4.773	.145	1	.703	6.156	.001 71189.816
	[F.L=3.0]	3.330	5.408	.379	1	.538	27.944	.001 1121668.533
[F.L=4.0]	.534	4.970	.012	1	.915	1.705	.000 28991.588	
[F.L=5.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.	
2.0	Intercept	-.337	4.899	.005	1	.945		
	Time	.054	.045	1.426	1	.232	1.055	.966 1.152
	M.Income	.000	.000	.066	1	.797	1.000	1.000 1.000
	[Gender=.0]	1.740	.993	3.070	1	.080	5.697	.814 39.891
	[Gender=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[Educ=1.0]	3.669	1.085	11.430	1	.001	39.218	4.674 329.064
	[Educ=2.0]	.281	.000	.	1	.	1.325	1.325 1.325
	[Educ=3.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[M.Status=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[M.Status=2.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.
	[F.L=.0]	1.521	18.057	.007	1	.933	4.576	1.951E-15 10736365946500938.000
	[F.L=1.0]	-2.810	4.356	.416	1	.519	.060	1.180E-5 306.890
	[F.L=2.0]	.061	4.671	.000	1	.990	1.063	.000 10050.467
	[F.L=3.0]	1.458	5.318	.075	1	.784	4.296	.000 144516.010
[F.L=4.0]	-.119	4.854	.001	1	.981	.888	6.552E-5 12039.348	
[F.L=5.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.	
3.0	Intercept	26.667	5.399	24.398	1	.000		
	Time	.060	.048	1.525	1	.217	1.062	.966 1.167
	M.Income	.000	.000	.210	1	.646	1.000	1.000 1.000
	[Gender=.0]	1.072	1.063	1.016	1	.313	2.920	.364 23.453
	[Gender=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0	.	.	.

	[Educ=1.0]	-27.911	1.255	494.873	1	.000	7.555E-13	6.460E-14	8.835E-12
	[Educ=2.0]	-27.906	.000	.	1	.	7.599E-13	7.599E-13	7.599E-13
	[Educ=3.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[M.Status=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[M.Status=2.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[F.L=.0]	4.881	18.152	.072	1	.788	131.755	4.662E-14	372328072994292610.000
	[F.L=1.0]	-3.267	4.881	.448	1	.503	.038	2.672E-6	544.156
	[F.L=2.0]	1.117	5.113	.048	1	.827	3.057	.000	68766.165
	[F.L=3.0]	3.170	5.705	.309	1	.578	23.809	.000	1708925.741
	[F.L=4.0]	1.944	5.270	.136	1	.712	6.989	.000	213820.938
	[F.L=5.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
4.0	Intercept	-7.464	5.586	1.785	1	.181	.	.	.
	Time	.125	.051	6.106	1	.013	1.134	1.026	1.252
	M.Income	.000	.000	.006	1	.940	1.000	1.000	1.000
	[Gender=.0]	.888	1.091	.663	1	.415	2.431	.287	20.621
	[Gender=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[Educ=1.0]	2.302	1.279	3.240	1	.072	9.998	.815	122.652
	[Educ=2.0]	2.238	.000	.	1	.	9.377	9.377	9.377
	[Educ=3.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[M.Status=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[M.Status=2.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[F.L=.0]	5.605	18.182	.095	1	.758	271.724	9.061E-14	814889376055385340.000
	[F.L=1.0]	-2.926	4.982	.345	1	.557	.054	3.078E-6	934.046
	[F.L=2.0]	1.434	5.222	.075	1	.784	4.197	.000	116861.268
	[F.L=3.0]	2.891	5.810	.248	1	.619	18.019	.000	1590180.287
	[F.L=4.0]	1.228	5.385	.052	1	.820	3.414	8.902E-5	130943.269
	[F.L=5.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
5.0	Intercept	-3.971	5.202	.583	1	.445	.	.	.
	Time	.062	.046	1.813	1	.178	1.064	.972	1.165
	M.Income	.000	.000	.014	1	.906	1.000	1.000	1.000
	[Gender=.0]	1.478	1.013	2.129	1	.145	4.384	.602	31.924
	[Gender=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[Educ=1.0]	2.528	1.112	5.171	1	.023	12.525	1.418	110.663
	[Educ=2.0]	.979	.000	.	1	.	2.661	2.661	2.661
	[Educ=3.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[M.Status=1.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[M.Status=2.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0
	[F.L=.0]	.583	20.498	.001	1	.977	1.792	6.386E-18	502675075038776900.000
	[F.L=1.0]	-.475	4.664	.010	1	.919	.622	6.665E-5	5806.796
	[F.L=2.0]	2.911	4.954	.345	1	.557	18.371	.001	302659.557
	[F.L=3.0]	1.824	5.637	.105	1	.746	6.197	9.863E-5	389299.880
	[F.L=4.0]	3.286	5.125	.411	1	.521	26.732	.001	615666.854
	[F.L=5.0]	0 ^b	.	.	0

a. The reference category is: .0.

b. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.

On the footnote of the SPSS output, we can see that the reference category of the dependent variable is set to zero, meaning that all other remaining categories are compared to this category. It is important to note that this category means that a client without any level of individual over-indebtedness status. The logistic coefficient (β) yields the information about the expected amount of change in the logit for each one-unit change in the predictor and the logit is what is being predicted; it is the odds of membership in the category of the outcome variable which has been specified (here the first value: 0 was specified, rather than the alternative values 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5). The explanatory variables that less influence the outcome variable in predicting the logit is characterized by the corresponding logistic coefficient that is closer to zero.

The predictors that less influence the outcome variable are monthly income, gender and marital status respectively while education, financial literacy and time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro are the predictors that influence at all individual over-indebtedness status. The other statistical metrics that are displayed in the table of parameter estimates are; the standard error, Wald statistic, df, Sig. (p-value); as well as the $\text{Exp}(\beta)$ and confidence interval for the $\text{Exp}(\beta)$.

The Wald test (and associated p-value) is used to evaluate whether or not the logistic coefficient is different from zero. The $\text{Exp}(\beta)$ is the odds ratio associated with each explanatory variable. The explanatory variables that increase the logit are characterized by $\text{Exp}(\beta)$ that is greater than 1.0, those which do not affect the logit are characterized by $\text{Exp}(\beta)$ of one unit (1.0) and explanatory variables which decrease the logit are characterized by $\text{Exp}(\beta)$ less than 1.0. In this regard, the predictor variable that does not affect the logit was monthly income.

Discussions of findings

The current study aims at assessing the impact of financial literacy on the individual over-indebtedness among the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro at the selected area under study. It was found that the staff of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro was composed of 4 (66.7%) males and 2 (33.3%) females. The current study revealed that most of the clients at SACCO Wisigara Rangiro in the area under study was married persons with a corresponding figure of 197 (55.2%) while the remaining part was single people with a corresponding number of 160 (44.8%).

The current study showed that most of the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro had completed only primary education 197 (55.2%), followed by those who completed secondary education 156 (43.7%) and then the minority of the clients have attended the university level 4 (1.1 %). The current study showed that the majority of the clients are aged between 31-41 years old with a corresponding figure of 170 (47.6 %), followed by clients aged > 41 years old 105 (29.4 %) and then the young people aged between 20-30 years old 82 (23.0 %).

This study yields the information about the level of financial literacy that the number of clients who do not know anything related to financial literacy at all was 9 (2.5%), those who had financial knowledge were 98 (27.5%), 81 (22.7%) had the financial skill, 58 (16.2%) had financial attitude, 75 (21.0%) had financial behaviour and 36 (10.1%) had financial awareness. With regards to the status of the individual over-indebtedness, the study revealed that 4 (1.1%) of the clients were out of the over-indebtedness status, 54 (15.1%) were in over-indebtedness status under the financial distress, 192 (53.8%) were in over-indebtedness status under regular arrears, 33 (9.2 %) were in the over-indebtedness status under foreclosure, 24 (6.7%) were in the over-indebtedness status under high debt to income ratio and 50 (14%) were in over-indebtedness status under the level of making heavy use of credit.

These results are similar to those of the studies conducted in Rwanda by Sayinzoga, Bulte and Lensink, 2014 and Tuyisenge, Mugambi and Kemirembe, 2015. The statistical test of the association of financial literacy and individual over-indebtedness revealed that these two variables were significantly associated. In comparison to the results found in the research conducted in Southern African countries by Ashenafi and Mutsonziwa, 2018, there were similar findings with this current research.

In this study, only three explanatory variables that influenced the outcome variable, and these were financial literacy with the corresponding statistical metrics Chi – square = 47.944, p – value = 0.004 < 0.05, education with Chi – square = 194.370, p – value = 0.000 < 0.05 and the time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro with Chi – square = 14.011, p – value = 0.016 < 0.05 respectively.

These results concurs with findings of the studies conducted by Irungu, Ogilo and Mwangi, 2016 in Kenya, Wamalwa, Rugiri & Lauer, 2019 in Kenya and Ashenafi and Mutsonziwa, 2018 in Southern African countries. Surprisingly, this study found that income doesn't contribute significantly to the individual over-indebtedness

and this conquers with the findings of a recent report conducted by Ashenafi and Mutsonziwa, 2018 in Southern African countries.

The responses from the interview guide on the description of the overall financial literacy of the clients recorded from the staff of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro revealed that the overall financial literacy of their clients was at a low level, and this was seen by the majority of the staff numbers;

Further on, 4 (66.6%) among six of staff who agreed that this level was low and this result was similar to the study conducted by Tuyisenge, Mugambi and Kemirembe, 2015 in Rwanda. On the training related issues of the clients, the staff of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro responded that there have been different training on the credit management processes but due to the lack of different skills and education-related issues as most of them have completed primary education only, their clients still miss this understanding even if such training has been offered to them.

Thus all staff members; 6 (100%) revealed that the main barrier that their clients face was the education level and this result agrees with that from the study conducted in Southern Africa countries by Ashenafi and Mutsonziwa, 2018. Due to the education as a main barrier and loan understanding related issues of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro clients, most of the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro 286 (80.1%) fail to manage their cash flows and multiple loans to honour their loan repayment.

Thus the staff still highlighting the problem of the education of their clients as a principal gap that prevents their clients to manage their cash flows and flows and multiple loans to honour their loan repayment. This finding correlates to the studies conducted in Southern Africa countries by Ashenafi and Mutsonziwa, 2018 and in Northern Ireland by French and McKillop, 2016.

Besides, the staff claimed that “all is about the lack of understanding which is a consequence of education barrier as stated earlier. With this big barrier of lack of skills from most of our clients who completed only primary education, our clients fail at all to compare interest rates and conditions of the loans with that of other financial institutions on then locality. This has affected them towards an over-indebtedness status. Some of them who could at least understand at a low level about the comparison between interest rates and conditions of the loans with that of other financial institutions in the locality are those who have a working experience of at least 3 years working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro. Thus, the more the client is experienced in working with us, the more she/he is in a timeline to compare interest rates and conditions of the loans with that of other financial institutions in the locality”. This finding showed that debt experience/working experience with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro has a significant effect on individual over-indebtedness and this has been the same resulted conclusion in the research conducted in Kenya by Irungu, Ogilo and Mwangi, 2016.

Again the staff stated that the level of over-indebtedness of their clients in the last five years has been varying from client to client. The clients that are considered to be in the over-indebtedness status were clients that can be referred to as newcomers in the services of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro. The clients that have been working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro for at least three years did not fall in over-indebtedness status at a high level compared to others, thus we note that the time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro affects individual over-indebtedness status. All the six 6 (100%) staff pointed out that this is an essential factor that contributed to the individual over-indebtedness status and this finding agrees with the results of a recent study done by Irungu, Ogilo and Mwangi, 2016 in Kenya.

Finally, the staff members of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro confirmed that financial knowledge, skills, attitude, behaviour and financial awareness are the main factors that contribute to individual over-indebtedness. This agreement has been stated by all the staff of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro, these factors can take on average 90% contribution on over-indebtedness status and this finding has been the same as the one resulted in the researches conducted by Sayinzoga, Bulte and Lensink, 2014 in Rwanda, Tuyisenge, Mugambi and Kemirembe, 2015 in

Rwanda, Wamalwa, Rugiri&Lauler, 2019 in Kenya, Ashenafi and Mutsonziwa, 2018 in Southern Africa countries, French and McKillop, 2016 and Begonia, Serrano and De la Cuesta, 2016 respectively.

Conclusion

Most people working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro in the year under study had primary education only and the people having attended the university level participate less in the services offered by SACCO Wisigara Rangiro and male people are participating in these services of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro than female people for the year of the study.

The level of financial literacy of the clients were assessed and found that most of the clients of SACCO Wisigara Rangiro have financial literacy under the category of financial knowledge and few people in this study were found to have no financial literacy at all. The researchers found that there was a significant association between financial literacy and the individual over-indebtedness status of the clients under study.

In establishing the relationship between financial literacy and the individual over-indebtedness, "education" was the first variable that came before financial literacy in explaining the outcome variable, and the main factors that influence all the individual over-indebtedness status of the clients were found to be education, financial literacy and the time spent working with SACCO Wisigara Rangiro for the year under study.

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